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TENDENCIES AND SCALE OF THE SHADOW ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article examines the current state of the shadow economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The methodology for assessing the shadow sector is outlined.

Key words: taxes, shadow economy, public finances, fiscal mechanism.

INTRODUCTION

The shadow economy in Uzbekistan has not been reflected in global rankings over the past five years. This does not indicate the complete absence of a shadow economy in the country but rather suggests that official authorities do not participate in international assessments of this phenomenon. Despite this, the issue of illegal trade remains relevant and continues to evolve.

The overall conclusion is that Uzbekistan's active participation in global rankings over the past five years is the result of state-adopted policies. Studies on the impact of the shadow economy on Uzbekistan's GDP from 2018–2021 have shown that its share is approximately 40–50%.

In September 2021, the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction held a conference on "The Shadow Economy in Uzbekistan: Assessment, Causes, and Ways of Reduction." During the event, problems related to this phenomenon were openly discussed, highlighting its significance and attracting the attention of many international experts. The President's statement before the High Council on this issue emphasized the importance of addressing and resolving this matter.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The integration of young people into the formal financial system by ensuring their participation has a positive impact on the economy. This is because official policymakers can more effectively implement monetary policy measures. Indeed, a higher level of financial inclusion enhances the efficient execution of interest rate policies, as noted by Mehrotra, A., and Yetman, J. Research has demonstrated that central banks can manage monetary policy more reliably and effectively when they have a broader base of agents within the formal financial system.

Additionally, financial inclusion facilitates a more efficient allocation of investments and portfolio decisions by financial agents. Therefore, greater financial inclusion can significantly influence inflation by improving the central bank's price stabilization mechanism.

Moreover, financial inclusivity enhances the stability of the financial system, as households and entrepreneurs can better adapt to changes in interest rates and credit conditions. Xon, H.R., and Tombini, A. emphasize that higher financial inclusion rates contribute to a more sustainable and fundamental monetary policy. Increased financial inclusion begins with directing cash flows from the public into bank deposits. This significantly strengthens the role of interest rates in operational control, as a larger portion of economic activity falls under interest rate oversight. When the informal sector is large, implementing and monitoring monetary policy becomes more challenging because small businesses and entrepreneurs make independent financial decisions that remain unaffected by central bank policies. Furthermore, financial inclusion facilitates the transition of individuals from the informal financial sector to the banking system, allowing them to track their financial transactions more effectively.

Mehrotra, A., and Yetman, J. highlight that as more agents integrate into the formal financial system, output volatility decreases relative to inflation, as financial agents can better adjust their investment and portfolio decisions. Thus, enhancing financial inclusion plays a crucial role in strengthening the central bank's price stabilization mechanism.

Furthermore, in some countries, inflation may be determined by a benchmark core price index, though this index is sometimes inaccurately selected. Mbutor, M.O., and Uba, I.A. examined the impact of monetary policy on financial inclusion and stability in Nigeria from 1980 to 2012. Their findings confirm the critical role of high levels of financial inclusion in strengthening and improving financial stability. However, an increase in the number of bank branches does not necessarily yield positive results, as banks often lack full independence in deposit-related decision-making. This suggests that the primary goal of opening new bank branches may not be to improve profitability but rather to expand financial operation opportunities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

If a request were made to the International Monetary Fund (IMF) to assess Uzbekistan's level of economic development based on the criteria set by the World Monetary Organization, comparable conditions could be observed in countries such as Ukraine and certain World Bank member states, including Gambia, Belize, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Honduras, and others.

As highlighted above, several methods exist for determining the level of economic development, and in this study, we apply them to evaluate Uzbekistan's economic progress. For this analysis, the Gutmann method, which is based on the relationship between cash and deposits, was employed. Using this method, the volume of cash in deposits from 1997 to 2018 was adjusted to estimate the scale of the developing economy. The modified cash flow adjustment method was applied for each year using a standard formula.

The base year was set as 1997, with the level of economic development initialized at zero. The model begins with a zero volume of the developing economy in 1997 and forecasts its growth over time. The ratio of cash to deposits was adjusted using the modified cash and deposit method throughout the period from 1997 to 2018.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

It is important to note that fluctuations in cash and deposit volumes do not necessarily indicate changes in demand, as these figures already account for the effects of inflation and population growth.

The coefficient of change in the cash-to-deposit ratio was calculated using a standard formula, applied to adjusted cash before meeting deposit demand. The findings revealed that between 2009 and 2018, 39.7 percent of the developing economy was generated in Uzbekistan.

Overall, the results indicate that the volume of the developing economy in Uzbekistan grew from 33.7 percent of the IMF benchmark in 2009 to 48 percent in 2018.

Figure 1. Based on data reflecting the relationship between cash and deposits, the exact amount of the developing economy has been determined.

The information presented in the figure above indicates that Uzbekistan's economy has exhibited a growth trend over the past few years. According to data from the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction, the volume of the developing economy accounted for 50% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2022.

Research findings suggest that since 2017, there has been a significant increase in the volume of the developing economy, primarily driven by the growth of cash and deposits. The supply of cash in the economy rose from 4.8% to 5.9% of GDP, while the share of cash in the total money supply increased from 24.9% in 2017 to 28.2% in 2018. It is worth noting that in 2020, the volume of the developing economy declined from 56.9% in 2018 to 48%, which also affected the dynamics of the money supply and its distribution. Thus, research results confirm that Uzbekistan has experienced a steady rise in cash transactions since 2017. Additionally, changes in the ratio of cash to deposits, based on simple relationships, serve as key indicators of the effectiveness of monetary policy.

The study further shows that the average volume of the developing economy in Uzbekistan is approximately 40% of GDP. Another factor influencing this volume is the additional amount of added value. The benefits derived from this added value depend on the capabilities of enterprises operating in this sector.

Moreover, Uzbekistan's refinancing rate is significantly lower than that of neighboring countries. For instance, while the refinancing rate in Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan stands at 12%, Uzbekistan maintains a considerably lower rate. This disparity is attributed to the greater opportunities available to Uzbek manufacturers. Consequently, this study examines the relationship between these two indicators.

The graph presented above demonstrates that state budget revenues from Value Added Tax (VAT) have followed a growing trend over the past five years. The reduction in the VAT rate from 20% to 15% has had a notable impact on tax revenues.

In this section of our monograph, we will conduct an empirical analysis to determine whether an increase in VAT revenue leads to economic growth or a decline. However, instead of employing a regression analysis, we will use a correlation coefficient to identify the relationship between these indicators.

Figure 2. The relationship between Value Added Tax (VAT) collection and the level of the shadow economy.

These indicators point to a strong positive correlation between Value Added Tax (VAT) collection and the growth of the shadow economy. This suggests that an increase in VAT revenues is accompanied by an expansion of informal economic activities. We can infer a positive relationship between the VAT rate and the size of the shadow economy, indicating that higher tax collection is associated with a broader informal sector.

At the same time, it is crucial to recognize that certain transactions within the shadow economy may remain unrecorded due to limitations in VAT accounting and collection mechanisms. Additionally, this policy may encourage formal entrepreneurial activity in sectors with diverse economic operations, where increasing VAT through regulatory measures could stimulate official business initiatives.

This policy may be particularly effective when it enhances the tax-paying capacity of market participants, as entrepreneurs boost their demand through higher consumption of goods and services. However, if the demand for goods and services does not grow or grows only slightly as a result of an increase in VAT, the policy will not yield the desired economic benefits.

In this context, tax authorities should evaluate how changes in VAT rates affect price fluctuations, taking into account the level of demand for goods and services.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, there is a positive correlation between VAT revenues and the size of the shadow economy. Information asymmetry plays a significant role, as businesses may underreport their income by providing less accurate or even misleading financial statements, ultimately reducing their tax liabilities. This, in turn, can hinder companies from accessing bank loans, thereby limiting their growth potential.

Within the shadow economy, entrepreneurs actively conceal their income and manipulate financial reports to avoid paying taxes and social contributions. The transaction transparency index also influences the extent of the shadow economy, as an increase in this index is linked to a rise in informal economic activities.

Tax revenues impact the size of the shadow economy, with higher tax collections often correlating with its expansion. However, excessively high taxes do not necessarily push businesses into the informal sector—if post-tax income remains insufficiently attractive, some enterprises may choose to operate outside the official economy. Therefore, policymakers must carefully balance tax policies to foster economic growth while minimizing incentives for businesses to shift into the shadow sector.

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